

**IDENTIFICATION OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS BY LC-MS/MS AND ANTIOXIDANT
ACTIVITY OF EXTRACTS OF KIGELIA AFRICANA FRUIT**

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ABSTRACT

Background: With a widespread distribution throughout Africa and a plethora of traditional uses, both medicinal and non-medical, *Kigelia africana* is a symbol of African herbal medicine. The main classes of chemicals that were identified were phenylethanoglycosides, terpenes, iridoids, flavonoids, and naphthoquinones. Strong antioxidant, antibacterial, and anticancer effects have been found in novel compounds, such as verbascoside, verminoside, and pinnatal, among others. **Objective:** The main aim of the study is to identify the phytoconstituents by FTIR and LCMS analysis and elaborate the antioxidant activity. **Method:** The extraction and fractionation processes were performed based on the polarity of the solvents. Additionally, FTIR and LCMS profiling were conducted using standard methods. The DPPH scavenging assay was employed to assess the antioxidant activity. **Results:** The Soxhlet extract and maceration extract were determined to have extractive values of 9% w/w and 8.4% respectively. The Total flavonoid content was found to be highest in the Soxhlet extraction, with a value of 6.4±0.173mg/QE of dry weight of extract. The presence of various functional groups in the extracts was confirmed by FTIR spectroscopy, indicating the presence of specific chemical bonds. Based on LCMS, thirty-eight compounds were identified in the maceration and soxhlet extraction. During the extraction process, it was observed that the Soxhlet process exhibited the highest antioxidant properties, with IC50 values of 14.1582 mg/mL. **Conclusion:** Based on the study's findings, it can be said that *Kigelia africana* holds promise as a herb for a number of different medical conditions.

KEYWORDS: *Kigelia Africana*, LCMS, FTIR, Soxhlet, maceration extraction.

INTRODUCTION

A rumored African traditional remedy, *Kigelia Africana* DC. is now widely available in India. It is a member of the Bignoniaceae family and has historically been used to treat a variety of illnesses. Among the many components that are utilized, root bark has been shown to have therapeutic qualities for gynecological ailments such as fibroid and uterine cancer, as well as biological activities including antioxidant, antimalarial, and antiprotozoal activity.^[1]

Plants such as *Kigelia africana* produce phytochemicals for a variety of purposes, such as defense against insect infestations, disease transmission, etc. *Kigelia Africana* bioactive molecules have been useful in identifying lead compounds for use in the creation of pharmaceuticals to

treat human ailments. Plant-based remedies are used by almost half of the world's population in Latin America, Asia, and Africa.^[2]

Kigelia africana fruit has a cylindrical shape, measuring 25 to 50 cm in length and 7.5 to 15 cm in width. The fruits are characterized by their woody texture and take on a greyish brown color when fully ripe. They have the ability to stay attached to the tree for a duration of up to one year. The weight of the fruit can reach a maximum of 3-3.5 kg.

The purpose of the study was to thoroughly investigate the biologically active ingredients in *Kigelia africana* fruit extract using liquid chromatography/mass spectroscopy (LC/MS). It was carried out with both

polarities in the ESI ionization mode. There are thirty-eight recognized chemicals in total positive mode. The molecules belong to the class group known as terpenoid, flavonoids, phenols, glycosides, and others. Among these molecules some have biological activities that include anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and anti-diabetic properties. The *Kigelia africana* fruit meal exhibited significant antioxidant characteristics.

To the best of our knowledge, despite the root of *Kigelia africana* having several traditional uses, not much has been published on its phytochemistry or therapeutic usage. The primary aim of this investigation was to employ Liquid Chromatography/Mass Spectroscopy, an effective analytical method, to thoroughly examine the biologically active components present in *K. africana* fruit bark extract. As a result, this study reveals the phytochemical profile of *K. Africana* fruit, highlighting its potential as a medicine for major human illnesses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

The *K. africana* fruit was collected from local market of Agra (27.1929° N, 78.0231° E). The plant was taxonomically identified from Raw Material Herbarium & Museum, Delhi, CSIR-NISCAIR as *Kigelia africana*. The fruit was gathered from the tree. Then it was shade-dried for ten days, crushed, and then ground using a grinder. The dried plant parts were crushed to produce coarse powder, which was kept in polythene airtight containers at room temperature for future use.^[3]

Reagents and Chemicals

All further compounds were analytical grade, unless noted otherwise. Aluminum chloride, Wagner's reagent, Mayer's reagent, Sodium hydroxide, Ferric chloride, Copper sulfate, n-Hexane, Quercetin, Ammonia liquid, Nitric acid, Sulphuric acid, Sodium carbonate, Ninhydrin, Chloroform (Fisher Scientific), Potassium hydroxide, Potassium bromide, Glacial acetic acid, Methanol (Qualigens-Thermo Fisher Scientific), Ethanol (Changshu Hongsheng Fine Chemical Co. Ltd.), Ethyl acetate (Finar Ltd.), DPPH (Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt Ltd., India).

Preparation of Extracts

The fruit of *Kigelia africana* was dried in the shade and ground into coarse powders weighing 500g. The powders were then extracted using 500 mL of ethanol by the soxhlet technique, and maceration process. Following a 24 hr. period, the crude extract underwent filtration and was subsequently evaporated to complete dryness using a water bath maintained at a temperature of 70 °C. An analysis was conducted on the desiccated residue of the unrefined extract.^[4]

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Estimation of TFC

A colorimetric test was used to determine the total flavonoid content (TFC). To 4 milliliters of distilled

water, 100 µL of extract was added. 0.3 mL of 5% sodium nitrite was then added. A 10% aluminum chloride solution (0.3 mL) was added after 5 minutes. 2 ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide was added to the mixture after 6 minutes. 3.3 cc of distilled water was added right away to dilute the mixture, and it was thoroughly mixed. In comparison to a blank, the absorbance at 510 nm was measured. The calibration curve was based on quercetin as the standard. The extract's total flavonoid concentration was given in mg of quercetin equivalents per gram of sample (mg/g).

By using established procedures, the phytoconstituents in *Kigelia africana* were screened out of the maceration and soxhlet extract.^[5]

FT-IR analysis

On the Shimadzu IRAffinity-1S FTIR spectrophotometer, FTIR spectra were recorded. With a 1 cm⁻¹ resolution, the scanning range was 4,500–400 cm⁻¹.

LCMS analysis

At Punjab University's Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Facility in Chandigarh, the LC-MS separation was carried out utilizing a Water Micro mass Quadrupole-ToF MS. The molecular weight of the structures that were previously known to be present in *Kigelia africana* fruit was used to identify each molecule from the reference compounds.^[6]

DPPH Scavenging Activities

Five distinct methanol concentrations (2, 4, 8, 16, and 32 mg/mL) were used to synthesize the plant extracts under investigation. They produced the same levels of ascorbic acid, a popular antioxidant. The examined extract solution (2.5 mL) and 1 mL of methanol were used as the starting point for the blank solutions. For the negative control, 1 mL of methanol and 2.5 mL of DPPH solution were used. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm following incubation. The tests were done three times. The IC₅₀ value was computed.^[7]

RESULTS

Plants contain a large number of secondary metabolites, according to research conducted using a range of techniques to profile their phytochemical profiles. FTIR, LCMS, and total flavonoid content were used in this work to profile the plants. The DPPH technique was used to measure antioxidant activity.

Extractive value

Kigelia africana fruits were collected and dried under shade and pulverized in desired size (#40). The results of extractive values of both the methods are given in table no. 1.

$$EV = \frac{\text{Dry weight of the extract}}{\text{Dry weight of the plant}} \times 100$$

Table No. 1: Extractive values of extracts.

Maceration Method (Ethanol 80%)-ME	Soxhlet Method (Ethanol 95%)-SE
8%	7.6%

2 displayed the outcomes of the preliminary phytochemical screen.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

The result of phytochemical screening showed that both the extracts are rich in secondary metabolites. Table No.

Table No. 2: Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of extracts.

Test	ME	SE
Alkaloid	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Phenols	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Steroids	-	+
Resins	+	+
Tannins	-	-
Carbohydrates	+	+
Saponin	-	-
Cardiac Glycosides	+	+
Proteins	-	-
Xanthoproteins	-	-

Total Flavonoid Content

Tables 3 and 4 represents the TFC of quercetin, which was estimated (Fig. 1) ($y = 0.0108x + 0.0806$ $R^2 = 0.9567$) and represented in QAE/g of dry extract weight

(Mean±SEM). Comparing soxhlet extraction (ME) to other extraction methods, the TFC of ME was the greatest at 6.4 ± 0.173 .

Table no. 3: Result of TFC (SE).

Extract Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Wt. of dry extract per ml in gm	Absorbance	Quercetin Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Quercetin Conc. (mg/mL)	TFC=cV/m	Mean ±SEM
1000	0.001	0.013	6.7	0.0067	6.7	6.4±0.173
1000	0.001	0.016	6.4	0.0064	6.4	
1000	0.001	0.019	6.1	0.0061	6.1	

Table no. 4: Result of TFC (ME).

Extract Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Wt. of dry extract per ml in gm	Absorbance	Quercetin Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Quercetin Conc. (mg/mL)	TFC=cV/m	Mean ±SEM
1000	0.001	0.027	5.3	0.0053	5.3	4.47±0.643
1000	0.001	0.031	4.9	0.0049	4.9	
1000	0.001	0.048	3.2	0.0032	3.2	

Figure 1: Standard curve of Quercetin.

FTIR interpretation

The FTIR analysis of maceration and soxhlet extraction methods of *Kigelia Africana* fruit (Table 5) confirmed the presence of aliphatic primary amines (N-H_(s)), Alkynes(C-H_(b)), ketones, organic Sulphur compounds (C=S_(s)), Amino acids, esters & lactones, mononuclear aromatic hydrocarbon (C-H_(b)), acid halides, carboxylic acid anhydride, lactams (C=O_(s)), alkanes, alkyl (C-H_(s)),

aromatic hydrocarbon (C-H_(s)), heteroaromatic (C-H_(s)), silicon compounds (SiO-H_(s)), amines (N-H_(b)), amine salts (N-H_(b)), ester (C-O_(s)), nitro compound (N-O_(s)), ether, epoxides, peroxides (C-O_(s)), nitrates (cis isomer N=O_(s)), alkenes, ketones, cyclic alkanes (C-H_(s)), alcohol & phenols (O-H_(s)), alkynes, sulfonamides (N-H_(s)), Phosphorous compounds(P-C_(s)), (Fig. 2-3) (Silverstein *et al.*, 2005).

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of ME.

Figure 3: FTIR spectrum of SE.

Table no. 6: FTIR spectrum interpretation.

S. No	Peak/Wave Number (cm-1)	Chemical Bond	Possible Functional group	Extract/ Fraction
1	879.85	C-C _(s)	Alkanes, Mononuclear & Polynuclear aromatic compound	SE,ME
2	1044.91	C-C _(s) , C-H _(b) , C-O _(s) , C-C(=O)-C _(b) , C-O _(s) , C-N _(s) , Si-H _(b)	Alkanes, Polynuclear aromatic compound, Alcohols & Phenols, Ketones, Esters & Lactones, Amines	SE,ME
3	1087.97	C-C _(s) , C-H _(b) , C-O _(s) , C-O _(s) , C-N _(s) , Si-H _(b)	Alkanes, Alcohols & Phenols, Esters & Lactones, Amines	SE,ME
4	2882.11	C-H _(s)	n- Alkanes, Methyl group, Methylene group	SE,ME
5	2973.97	C-H _(s) , C-H _(s)	n- Alkanes, Methylene group, Ether, Epoxides, Peroxides	SE
6	1379.34	C-H _(b)	Branched chain Alkanes	SE,ME

7	610.01	C-H _(b)	Alkynes	SE
8	677.47	C-H _(b)	Alkynes, Mononuclear aromatic compound	SE,ME
9	687.51	C-H _(b)	Alkynes, Mononuclear & Polynuclear aromatic compound	SE,ME
10	1339.15	C-H _(b) , C-C(=O)-C _(s) , N-O _(s) , S=O _(s)	Alkynes, Ketones, Covalent compound, Sulfones	SE,ME
11	1379.34	O-H _(b) , N-O _(s)	Alcohols & Phenols, Covalent compound	SE,ME
12	1273.12	C-H _(b) , C-C(=O)-C _(s) , C-O _(s)	Mononuclear aromatic compound, Ketones, Esters & Lactones	SE,ME
13	3337.10	C-H _(s) , N-H _(s)	Ether, Epoxides, Peroxides, Amines	SE
14	720.53	C-H _(b) , C-S _(b) , C-S _(s) , P-C _(s)	Alkynes, Mononuclear Aromatic hydrocarbons, Organic Sulphur compounds, Phosphorous compounds	SE,ME
15	816.69	C-H _(b) , Si-H	Mononuclear Aromatic hydrocarbons, Silicon compounds	SE,ME
16	881.28	C-H _(b) , Si-H	Mononuclear Aromatic hydrocarbons, Silicon compounds	SE,ME
17	951.61	Si-H	Silicon compounds	ME
18	1092.27	C-O-C, C-O _(s) , Si-O _(b)	Ethers, Epoxides, Peroxides, Esters & Lactones, Silicon compounds	ME
19	1178.39	C-O _(s) , C-C(=O)-C _(s) , C-C(=O)-C _(b) , C-O _(s) , C-N _(s)	Ethers, Epoxides, Peroxides, Amines, Ketones, Esters & Lactones	SE,ME
20	1194.18	C-C-O, C-C(=O)-C _(s) , C-C(=O)-C _(b) , C-O _(s) , C-N _(s)	Ethers, Epoxides, Peroxides, Ketones, Esters & Lactones, Amines	SE,ME
21	1220.02	C-H _(b) , C-O _(s) , O-H _(b) , C-C(=O)-C _(s) , C-O _(s) , C-O _(s) , C-N _(s)	Ketones, Alkynes, Amines Alcohols & Phenols, Carboxylic acid, Esters & Lactones,	SE,ME
22	1362.11	C-H _(b) , O-H _(b) , O-H _(b) , S=O _(s)	Branched chain alkanes, Alkynes, Alcohols & Phenols, Carboxylic acid, Sulfonamides	SE,ME
23	1416.65	C-H _(b) , O-H _(b) , O-H _(b)	N-Alkanes, Cycloalkenes, Alcohols & Phenols, Carboxylic acid	ME
24	1420.96	C-H _(b) , O-H _(b)	N-Alkanes, Alcohols & Phenols, Carboxylic acid	ME
25	1425.27	C-H _(b) , O-H _(b)	N-Alkanes, Carboxylic acid	ME
26	1432.44	C-H _(b) , O-H _(b)	N-Alkanes, Carboxylic acid	ME
27	1438.18 9	C-H _(b) , O-H _(b)	N-Alkanes, Carboxylic acid	ME
28	1709.46	C=O _(s)	Carboxylic acid	ME
29	1735.29	C=O _(s)	Esters & Lactones, Amides & Lactams, Ketones	SE,ME
30	1741.03	C=O _(s)	Esters & Lactones, Amides & Lactams	SE,ME
31	1743.90	C=O _(s)	Esters & Lactones, Amides & Lactams, Ketones	SE,ME
32	2854.84	C-H _(b) , O-H _(s)	Cyclic alkanes, Carboxylic acid, Amino acids,	ME
33	2926.60	O-H _(s)	Carboxylic acid, Amino acids	ME

(b):- Bending, (s):- Stretching**Liquid chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy (LC/MS) Analysis**

The chromatogram detected 38 components, which are shown in Table 6. The identities of the compounds were confirmed by examining the mass/charge [m/z] data and comparing it with previously released information. Various secondary metabolites were identified from the LCMS data which includes the phenolic compounds (balaphonin, caffeic acid, p-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, luteolin, kigeliol, 6-p-coumaroyl-sucrose), steroids (β -sitosteron, stigmasterol), triterpenes (oleanolic acid,

phytol), Quinones (pinnatal, norviburtibnal), Iridoids (jiofuran, jioglutolide), Alkanes (n-hentriacontane, tritriacontane), Esters (hydroxyphenyl ethyl ester), Unsaturated Fatty acids, Fig. 4 and 5. Apart from the thirty-eight identified compounds from the extracts, twelve molecules have reported biological activities (Table 7).

Table no.7: Characterization of LC-MS/MS of Extract.

SN	m/z	Molecular Formula	Mol. wt.g.mol ⁻¹	RT (Min.)	Identified Compound	Classification	Extract/Fraction
1	165.05	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	164.16	36.42	p-Coumaric acid	Phenolic Compounds	SE,ME
2	181.04	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄	180.16	32.83	Caffeic acid	Phenolic Compounds	SE,ME
3	133.06	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄	194.18	3.08	Ferulic acid	Phenolic Compounds	SE,ME
4	289.08	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.23	23.23	Luteolin	Phenolic Compounds	ME
5	423.23	C ₁₂ H ₂₃ O ₁₄ P	422.28	23.09	6-p-coumaroyl-sucrose	Phenolic Compounds	SE,ME
6	239.09	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅	238.24	28.79	Kigeliol	Phenolic Compounds	SE,ME
7	357.22	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆	356.40	19.12	Balaphonin	Phenolic Compounds	SE,ME
8	209.08	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄	208.21	3.05	8-hydroxy-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin	Coumarins	SE,ME
9	415.15	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O	414.71	2.70	β-Sitosterol	Sterols	ME
10	413.11	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O	412.70	25.24	Stigmasterol	Sterols	SE,ME
11	457.15	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃	456.71	31.93	Oleanolic acid	Triterpenes	SE,ME
12	281.05	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	296.53	39.87	Phytol	Triterpenes	SE,ME
13	257.26	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂	294.50	32.89	(9Z,12Z)-Methyl octadeca-9,12-dienoate	Unsaturated Fatty acids	SE,ME
14	243.07	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃	242.27	18.68	Lapachol	Quinones	SE,ME
15	241.06	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃	240.30	15.22	Dehydro α-lapachone	Quinones	SE
16	339.24	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅	338.11	22.10	Pinnatal	Quinones	SE,ME
17	147.04	C ₉ H ₆ O ₂	146.14	23.09	Norviburtinal	Quinones	SE,ME
18	243.07	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	242.23	40.01	2-(1-Hydroxyethyl)-naphtho[2,3-b] furan-4,9-quinone	Quinones	SE,ME
19	189.16	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	188.22	37.75	7-hydroxy-10-deoxyeucommiol	Iridoids	SE,ME
20	173.12	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₃	172.22	19.31	10-Deoxyeucommiol	Iridoids	SE,ME
21	185.12	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₄	184.00	29.10	Jiofuran	Iridoids	SE
22	189.16	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	188.22	29.37	3-(2-hydroxyethyl)-5-(2-hydroxypropyl)-4,5-dihydrofuran-2(3H)-one	Iridoids	SE,ME
23	241.06	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₆	240.21	34.00	7-hydroxyeucommic acid	Iridoids	SE
24	189.16	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	188.22	31.11	7-hydroxy eucommiol	Iridoids	SE,ME
25	187.14	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	186.20	27.77	Jioglutolide	Iridoids	SE,ME
26	187.14	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	186.21	27.89	Des-p-hydroxy benzoyl kisasagenol B	Iridoids	SE,ME
27	511.37	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₁₂	510.48	20.61	6-Trans-caffeoyl ajugol	Iridoids	SE
28	525.46	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₁₃	524.54	22.84	Verminoside	Iridoids	SE
29	509.19	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₁₂	508.50	28.40	Specioside	Iridoids	SE,ME
30	177.05	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ O ₁₃	538.51	28.34	Minecoside	Iridoids	SE,ME
31	437.2	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	436.85	32.47	n-hentriacontane	Alkanes	ME
32	367.2	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	366.70	31.37	11-(2,2-dimethylpropyl) heneicosane	Alkanes	SE,ME
33	185.12	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	184.36	29.10	4,4-dimethylundecane	Alkanes	SE

34	353.22	C ₁₆ H ₃₃ I	352.34	32.78	1-iodohexadecane	Alkanes	SE,ME
35	465.1	C ₃₃ H ₆₈	464.90	34.96	Tritriacontane	Alkanes	SE
36	437.2	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	436.85	32.47	Hentriacontane	Alkanes	ME
37	409.25	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	408.79	25.78	Nonacosane	Alkanes	SE,ME
38	181.08	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	180.27	32.83	2-(4-hydroxyphenyl) ethyl ester	Esters	SE,ME

Table no. 7: Reported biological activities of identified molecules.

S.no	Predicted Compounds	Biological Activity	References
1	p-Coumaric acid	antimicrobial activities, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory	[8]
2	Caffeic acid	anti-inflammatory and anticancer activities	[9]
3	Ferulic acid	antioxidant, anticarcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, and antiviral activity	[10]
4	Luteolin	antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities	[11]
5	β-Sitosterol	anticancer effect	[12]
6	Stigmasterol	anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, and anti-allergy	[13]
7	Oleanolic acid	antioxidant, anticancer, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and anti-asthmatic activities	[14]
8	Phytol	anti-bacterial	[15]
9	Lapachol	immunosuppressive, contraceptive, antimicrobial, antiulcer, anticancer, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, trypanocidal, leishmanicidal, molluscicidal, and antifungal activities	[16]
10	Pinnatal	Potent oxidative radical scavenging and antioxidant activity against DPPH free radicals	[17]
11	Verminoside	Sensitizes cisplatin-resistant cancer cells and suppresses metastatic growth of human breast cancer	[18]
12	Specioside	anti-inflammatory	[19]

Figure 4: LCMS Chromatogram of ME of *Kigelia africana* fruit Extract.

Figure 5: LCMS Chromatogram of SE of *Kigelia african* fruit Extract.

Antioxidant activity by DPPH Method

The plant extracts were evaluated for their antioxidant activity by measuring their capacity to decrease the stable DPPH free radical. The extracts were diluted in a series to obtain concentrations of 2, 4, 8, 16 and 32 mg/mL. A 100 μ L portion of a methanol solution containing 0.16 mM DPPH was combined with 200 μ L

of different doses of each extract. A control solution was made without including any plant material. The spectrophotometer was used to measure the absorbance at a specific wavelength of 515 nm. The measurements were conducted three times and then averaged. The ability of the extracts to scavenge DPPH radical was calculated (Table no. 7).

Table No. 7: Free radical scavenging activity of extracts.

SN	Conc. (mg/mL)	Ascorbic acid	SE	ME
1	2	16.01±0.27	13.19±0.31	09.51±0.32
2	4	23.03±0.39	18.58±0.34	11.14±0.06
3	8	37.75±0.12	25.55±0.24	19.62±0.41
4	16	70.68±0.56	44.23±0.18	36.12±0.44
5	32	89.91±0.26	67.66±0.32	49.42±0.06
IC ₅₀ value	14.1582 mg/mL			

Figure 6: DPPH scavenging activity.

Figure 7: Chemical structures of bioactive compounds.

DISCUSSION

This study used maceration and soxhlet extraction to extract the fruit of *Kigelia africana*. Every extract was given an extractive value (% w/w), with the Soxhlet extraction having the greatest extractive value (8 %). Because the soxhlet process recycles fresh solvent and operates at high temperatures, it enhances the mass transfer rate. Sonolysis, cell membrane disruption, and the extraction of intracellular secondary metabolites are the results of these forces. Using a variety of conventional techniques, the preliminary phytochemical screening of the maceration extract and soxhlet extraction was also carried out. The results indicate the existence of several secondary metabolites, including cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, flavonoids, and alkaloids. The maximum flavonoid content was found in the SE fraction (6.4 ± 0.173 mg GAE/g) according to the TFC result, followed by the SE fraction (4.47 ± 0.643 GAE/g). As per the TFC results, *K. africana* fruit is a fruit that is rich in flavonoid compounds. These compounds will be used in future pharmacological investigations related to diseases including Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, cardiovascular, and numerous inflammatory and lifestyle disorders caused by oxidative stress³³.

FTIR analysis revealed that the -OH and C=O functional groups seen in the extracts were consistently present. The SE revealed peaks at 2973, 3337, 1362, 1735, 1743, and 879 cm^{-1} , which were linked to lactams, alkanes, heteroaromatic, aromatic hydrocarbons, alcohol & phenols, epoxy, lactones, acid halides, and carboxylic acid anhydride. It was discovered that the FTIR

interpretation and the LCMS data were associated. Liquid chromatography Using mass spectroscopy, one may identify, measure, and perform a mass analysis of a variety of inorganic or organic molecules that are either non-volatile or semi-volatile in a mixture. Another useful technique for examining complex plant extracts is the combination of mass spectrometry and liquid chromatography (LC/MS). Among hyphenated approaches, it is an extremely powerful and sophisticated instrument for identifying low and high molecular weight research. One major advantage of ESI is its ability to provide mild ionization in LCMS. The hydro-ethanolic extract's LCMS chromatogram is shown in Fig. The degree of similarity between the molecular mass and molecular weight was used to identify the extracted and fractionated molecules. There were 38 chemicals found in all. Ep-Coumaric acid, or phenolic compound (m/z 165.05; 36.42 min), was the first compound to elute. Similarly, luteolin (m/z 289.08), 6-p-coumaroyl-sucrose (m/z 423.23), kigeliol (m/z 239.09), balaphonin (m/z 357.22), and caffeic acid (m/z 181.04) are other cardiac glycosides. Other compounds such as coumarin 8-hydroxy-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-methyl-3, and 4-dihydroisocoumarin (m/z 209.08) were also eluted at 3.05 minutes, in that order. Additionally, additional substances such as β -Sitosterol (m/z 415.15) and Stigmasterol (m/z 413.11) were also eluted at 2.70 and 25.24 minutes. Additionally, additional molecules such as phytonolic acid (m/z 281.05) and oleanolic acid (m/z 457.15) were also eluted from triterpenes at 31.93 and 39.87 minutes. At 32.89 minutes, 9Z,12Z)-Methyl octadeca-9,12-dienoate (m/z 257.26), an unsaturated

fatty acid, was eluted. Additionally, several Quinones were also eluted, including 2-(1-Hydroxyethyl)-naphtho[2,3-b] furan-4,9-quinone (m/z 243.07), Dehydro α -lapachone (m/z 241.06), Pinnatal (m/z 339.24), and Norviburtinal (m/z 147.04) at 18.68, 15.22, 22.10, 23.09, and 40.01 minutes. In addition, various iridoids, such as 7-hydroxy-10-Deoxyeucommiol (m/z 189.16), Jiofuran (m/z 185.12), and 10-Deoxyeucommiol (m/z 173.12) 3-(Ethyl-2-hydroxy)2-hydroxypropyl)-5-2-(3H)-one, or -4,5-dihydrofuran (m/z 189.16), Des-p-hydroxy benzoyl kisasagenol B (m/z 187.14), Jioglutolide (m/z 187.14), 7-hydroxyeucommic acid (m/z 241.06), and 7-hydroxy eucommiol (m/z 189.16), Sixth, trans-caffeoyl ajugol (m/z 511.37), verminoside (m/z 525.46), specioside (m/z 509.19), and minecoside (m/z 177.05) at 37.75, 19.31, 29.10, 29.37, 34.00, 31.11, 27.77, 27.89, 20.61, 22.84, 28.40, and 28.34 minutes. Additionally, a few other alkanes were also eluted, including n-hentriacontane (m/z 437.0), 11-(2,2-dimethylpropyl) heneicosane (m/z 367.20), 4,4-dimethylundecane (m/z 185.12), 1-iodohexadecane (m/z 353.22), Tritriacontane (m/z 465.10), Hentriacontane (m/z 437.20), and Nonacosane (m/z 409.25) at 32.47, 31.37, 29.10, 32.78, 34.96, 32.47, 25.78 min. Additionally, one ester (the 2-(4-hydroxyphenyl) ethyl ester; m/z 181.08) is eluted at 32.83 minutes.

The yield and composition of bioactive chemicals, such as flavonoids and phenolic compounds, derived from plant sources are significantly influenced by the extraction technique used. Research have demonstrated that the antioxidant activity of these compounds can be strongly impacted by the extraction solvent used. Antioxidant molecules from plant materials are frequently extracted using polar and medium-polar solvents, such as water, ethanol, methanol, and their aqueous mixes. Comparing soxhlet extraction to maceration, a more straightforward extraction procedure, it has been found that the former produces greater concentrations of flavonoids and phenolic chemicals due to its repeated cycles of solvent evaporation and condensation. The Soxhlet method's superior solubilization and recovery of these bioactive chemicals accounts for the observed difference in extraction efficiency. Plant extracts exhibit a clear correlation between their quantity of flavonoids and phenolic components and their antioxidant properties. Because Soxhlet extracts contain more of these chemicals than maceration extracts, it has been discovered that Soxhlet extracts have a stronger antioxidant capacity.

CONCLUSIONS

Research interest in *K. africana* has increased due to its acknowledged medicinal potential. Many of its traditional medical use, however, have not yet been the subject of scientific investigation. The present study provided valuable insights into the antioxidant potential of *Kigelia Africana* fruit extracts. The results indicate that the extract exhibited potent antioxidant activity, which could be attributed to the presence of bioactive

compounds such as polyphenols. More investigation into the existential studies on its pharmacological action is advised in future.

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